

FUZZY CONTROLLER FOR AUTOMATIC ADJUSTEMENT OF THE ELECTROMECHANICAL POSITION DRIVE TRAJECTORY

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This paper describes the development of a methodology to synthesize fuzzy controllers to correct the tracking dynamics of an electromechanical positioning drive trajectory.

A brief introduction to tubular linear synchronous motors is presented.

Special focus is made on parallel manipulators using tubular linear synchronous permanent magnet motors, where computer simulations confirmed large amplitude variations of load forces applied to linear actuators of an existing six degrees of freedom (6 DOF) parallel manipulator.

The fuzzy controller synthesis for the linear position drive is described. Its main goal is to perform the automatic adjustment of the tubular linear motor positioning trajectory, by changing its speed and acceleration references. The laboratory prototype and the experimental results of the fuzzy controller coupled to the electromechanical linear position drive are presented and discussed.

Keywords: Tubular Linear Motor, 6 DOF parallel manipulator, Fuzzy Control, Positioning Trajectory Adjustment

1. Introduction

The electromechanical position drive presents in this paper is based on Permanent Magnet Tubular Linear Synchronous Motor (PM-TLSM) as the electromechanical linear actuator fed by a position drive controller and a linear encoder as feedback device of the system. The mathematical models of the PM-TLSM and the position drive controller used in this work are present in [1] and [2], respectively.

The linear motors are employed in a wide range of electromechanical systems, such as robotics and factory automation, processing and packaging equipment, machine tools, transfer equipment, aerospace industry and transportation systems. An industrial applications issue of the linear actuators is present in [3]. The linear motor applies force directly to the load, and does not require any intermediate mechanism to convert rotary motion into linear motion. Linear motors are capable of high speeds, fast acceleration, and accurate positioning and they can offer significant advantages over conventional linear motion systems, such as hydraulic linear

actuators, motors drives by cams, ballscrews and belts. Advantages are higher efficiency, low cost maintenance, no power loss in rotary-linear conversion, speed and force control and positional accuracy [4].

2. Tubular Linear synchronous motor

The linear machines are derived using rotary machines knowledge. Geometrically, rotary machines can be “cut” along the radial plane and “unrolled”. This is exemplified in Figure 1(a) and Figure 1(b). Applying this process to a PM rotary synchronous motor a PM flat LSM is obtained Figure 1(b). The PM-TLSM can be developed from flat linear motors by “rolling” them around their longitudinal axis. The permanent magnets, initially oriented along the length of the linear shaft, now form a stack of alternating magnetic polarity rings, Figure 1(c).

Figure 1- (a) Rotary motor; (b) Flat linear motor; (c) Tubular linear motor.

The PM-TLSM used in this work is the CLD4206D model from California Linear Devices, Inc. The Figure 2 illustrates a cutaway view of the CLD4206D tubular linear motor, showing the shaft containing rings of rare-earth neodymium-iron-boron magnets.

Figure 2- A cutaway view of the PM-TLSM.

The magnetic field provides the interaction between stator coils and the moving part. This characteristic gives a very accurate method for achieving force and motion control.

2.1 6 DOF parallel manipulator

The 6 DOF parallel manipulators are wide used for the support of flight simulators, and are often designed to emulate the aeronautic motions.

Considering a three-dimension system coordinates given by directions X, Y, and Z, the 6 DOF moves can be represented as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3- Representation of the six degrees of freedom; (a) translation moves; (b) rotary moves.

In Figure 3(a), the labels surge, sway and heave, represents the translation moves according to the axes X, Y, Z, respectively.

In Figure 3(b), the labels roll, pitch and yaw, represents the rotation moves according to the axes X, Y, Z, respectively.

The commercial 6 DOF parallel manipulators usually employ hydraulic linear actuators. The hydraulic linear actuators have higher volume/power ratio than tubular linear synchronous motors and higher maintenance costs.

2.1.1 Forces applied to the electromechanical linear actuators

The Figures 4 to 6 shows the simulations results obtained with the 6 DOF parallel manipulator model in steady-state conditions, for some 6 DOF extreme positions, with 2000N load force on the top platform of the parallel manipulator.

The simulations results are obtained through the simulation software MD Nastran™ developed by MSC.Software®. This simulation software use all the elements physic characteristics of the parallel manipulator. All the elements are projected in CAD environment and imported to MD Nastran™.

As it can be seen in Figures 4 to 6, the linear actuators have to withstand large variations of the load force according to the top platform position.

Figure 4- Initial position of the parallel manipulator.

Figure 5- Surge translation by $-0,27$ m .

Figure 6- Roll rotation by $-0,44$ rad .

The Table 1 resumes the simulations results for minimum and maximum forces of the linear actuators obtained in 6 DOF extreme positions.

Table 1- Forces applied to the linear actuators.

6 DOF moves	Value	Minimum Force (N)	Maximum Force (N)
Roll	0,44rad	83	738
Pitch	-0,42rad	106	749
Yaw	0,56rad	126	642
Surge	-0,27m	83	763
Sway	-0,24m	0	719
Heave	0m	410	

3. Trajectory fuzzy controller

This paper considers the control of one of the 6 DOF of the mechanical system, in which a PM-TLSM is used as the linear electromechanical actuator. Since fuzzy logic controllers are based on heuristics, they

are able to incorporate human intuition and experience. The resulting motion trajectory obtained from the fuzzy controller is particularly suited to high accuracy applications such as parallel manipulators, robotics systems and factory automation. The experimental results obtained verify the effectiveness of the proposed scheme.

3.1 Fuzzy controller

In recent years the fuzzy control has been increasingly developed and has become one of the most successful industry tools.

Fuzzy logic control provides a formal methodology for representing, manipulating and implementing a human's heuristic knowledge on how to control a system [5].

Figure 10 shows the main components of the fuzzy controller.

Figure 10- Block diagram of the fuzzy controller.

The inputs are most often hard or crisp measurements from some measuring equipment, rather than linguistic. A pre-processor block adjusts the measurements before they enter the fuzzy controller, [6]. Examples of pre-processing are:

- Quantisation in connection with sampling or rounding to integers;
- Normalisation or scaling into a particular, standard range;
- Filtering in order to remove noise;
- A combination of several measurements to obtain key indicators;
- Differentiation and integration or their discrete equivalences.

The “fuzzification” interface modifies the inputs so that, they can understand and activate the rules in the “rule-base”. There is a degree of membership for each linguistic term that applies to that input variable.

The “rule-base” holds the knowledge, in the form of a set of rules, i.e. the way to control the system. The Fuzzy logic incorporates a simple, rule-based “IF X AND Y THEN Z” approach to solve the control problem rather than attempting to model a system mathematically. The fuzzy logic model is empirically-based, relying on the operator's experience, not necessarily aided by the technical understanding of the system.

The “inference engine” evaluates which control rules are appropriate at the current time and then decides what input should be applied to the process. Just as we humans use many different types of differential procedures to help us to make decisions, there are many different fuzzy logic inferential procedures. In engineering applications of fuzzy controllers, only a few numbers of them are actually being used [6].

The “defuzzification” interface converts the conclusions reached by “inference engine” into the process inputs. The resulting fuzzy set is thus defuzzified into a crisp control signal. There are several defuzzification methods, [6].

The post-processing block makes an output scaling. In case the output is defined on a standard universe this must be scaled to engineering units. The post-processing block often contains an output gain that can be tuned, and sometimes also an integrator in some types of fuzzy controllers.

3.2 The fuzzy controller design methodology

The design methodology of the fuzzy controllers can be reached with five fundamental steps, [7]:

- Select the performance (control and solution) variables;
- Define the control surfaces (the fuzzy sets);
- Devise the relationship between input and output spaces (rules);
- Run a simulation of the system model;
- Interpret the output (defuzzify to get expected values);

The fuzzy modelling of information systems involves a relatively simple process. The control surface is designed to respond correctly to a set of expected data points. This control surface (the system response) is made to react correctly to the input of the system, by changing either the shape of the fuzzy sets and/or the consequence of the rules (the system relationships).

3.2.1 Definition of the system parameters

The global control scheme, Figure 11, uses one fuzzy controller with three inputs and two outputs to predict the necessary speed and acceleration references that allow the system to track the position reference correctly.

The variables to control are the change of speed reference, Δv_{ref} , and the change of acceleration reference, Δa_{ref} .

As it is shown on Figure 11, the outputs of the fuzzy controller, Δv_{ref} and Δa_{ref} , are summed with the speed and acceleration references, v_{ref} and a_{ref} , respectively.

Figure 11- Global control scheme to correct the electromechanical position drive trajectory using the fuzzy controller.

The resulting values are the new speed and acceleration values, v'_{ref} and a'_{ref} , which are described by (1) and (2), respectively.

$$\begin{cases} v'_{ref} = v_{ref} + \Delta v_{ref} & \text{if } |v'_{ref}| < v_{max} \\ v'_{ref} = v_{max} & \text{if } v'_{ref} > 0 \text{ and } |v'_{ref}| \geq v_{max} \\ v'_{ref} = -v_{max} & \text{if } v'_{ref} < 0 \text{ and } |v'_{ref}| \geq v_{max} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{cases} a'_{ref} = a_{ref} + \Delta a_{ref} & \text{if } |a'_{ref}| < a_{max} \\ a'_{ref} = a_{max} & \text{if } a'_{ref} > 0 \text{ and } |a'_{ref}| \geq a_{max} \\ a'_{ref} = -a_{max} & \text{if } a'_{ref} < 0 \text{ and } |a'_{ref}| \geq a_{max} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The v'_{ref} and a'_{ref} values are the modified references for the electromechanical position drive, which correct the tracking trajectory of the positioning system.

In (1) and (2), v_{max} and a_{max} are the limiter values for speed and acceleration that can be set into the electromechanical position drive for a specific application.

In the position control loop, the fuzzy input variables are the position, speed and acceleration errors, e_x , e_v and e_a , respectively.

The speed error, e_v , can be interpreted as the change of position error, and the acceleration error, e_a , as the change of the speed error.

In order to assure the simplicity of the fuzzy controller, the shapes of the membership functions adopted for the fuzzification of the inputs and outputs are triangular and trapezoidal.

The fuzzy linguistic inputs (e_x , e_v and e_a) are covered by five fuzzy sets: Negative Big (NG), Negative (N),

Zero (ZE), Positive (P) and Positive Big (PG), as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12- Membership functions of the fuzzy controller inputs.

The fuzzy linguistic outputs (Δv_{ref} and Δa_{ref}) include nine fuzzy sets: Enormous (E), Big (G), Medium (M), Small (P), which can assume positive or negative values and Zero (ZE), as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13- Membership functions of the fuzzy controller outputs.

The fuzzy inference engine used is the MAX-MIN method [6], which tests the magnitudes of each rule and selects the highest one.

The defuzzification method employed is the COG (center of gravity), [6].

3.2.2 Rule formulation

To obtain the control rules, a typical second order dynamic system response to a step input is taking into account [8], as seen in Figure 14.

Figure 14- Typical second order system response.

The Figure 14 is splitted into four distinct sectors. The differences of each sector can be evaluated by the error (e) and the change of error (Δe) signals. For the first sector the error and the change of error signals are described by (3).

$$\text{sector 1: } e > 0, \Delta e < 0 \quad (3)$$

For the remaining sectors, the error and the change of error signals are given from (4) to (6).

$$\text{sector 2: } e < 0, \Delta e < 0 \quad (4)$$

$$\text{sector 3: } e < 0, \Delta e > 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{sector 4: } e > 0, \Delta e > 0 \quad (6)$$

The control strategy is achieved by building the rule bases. This rule bases consider the desired dynamic system behaviour, i.e. considers overshoot, rising time, settling time, position and speed errors and the respective error changes.

The total number of the rules is 125. The rule that perform the control objective of this fuzzy controller is given by (7).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{If } e_x = \text{ZE} \text{ and } e_v = \text{ZE} \text{ and } e_a = \text{ZE} \\ \text{then } \Delta v_{ref} = \text{vZE} \text{ and } \Delta a_{ref} = \text{aZE} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

When the fuzzy controller is executing only the rule described by (7), the electromechanical position drive trajectory is correct.

The opposite situation occurs when the position error is positive or negative big for any values of speed and acceleration errors. The control solution, to achieve fast response in trajectory adjustment, is activating the speed and acceleration limiters. The rules given by (8) and (9) explain this condition.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{If } e_x = \text{PG} \text{ and } \forall e_v \text{ and } \forall e_a \\ \text{then } \Delta v_{ref} = \text{vE} \text{ and } \Delta a_{ref} = \text{aE} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{If } e_x = \text{NG} \text{ and } \forall e_v \text{ and } \forall e_a \\ \text{then } \Delta v_{ref} = -\text{vE} \text{ and } \Delta a_{ref} = \text{dE} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

When the fuzzy controller is executing the rules described by (8) or (9), the correction action for the electromechanical position drive trajectory consists to apply all the available force to get out this situation.

The remaining rules of the fuzzy controller are obtained by simulation of the mathematical model of the electromechanical position drive, according to the experimental knowledge of its dynamic behaviour, [9]. Those rules are summarized in Tables 1 to 4.

Table 1- Rule table for any e_a .

Δv_{ref}		e_v				
		NG	N	ZE	P	PG
e_x	PG	vE	vE	vE	vE	vE
	P	-vM	vZE	vP	vM	vG
	ZE	-vM	-vP	vZE	vP	vM
	N	-vG	-vM	-vP	vZE	vM
	NG	-vE	-vE	-vE	-vE	-vE

Table 2- Rule table for $e_x = P$.

Δa_{ref}		e_a				
		NG	N	ZE	P	PG
e_v	PG	aP	aM	aG	aE	aE
	P	aZE	aP	aM	aG	aE
	ZE	dM	aZE	aP	aM	aG
	N	dM	dP	aZE	aP	aM
	NG	dG	dM	dP	aM	aP

Table 3- Rule table for $e_x = N$.

Δa_{ref}		e_a				
		NG	N	ZE	P	PG
e_v	PG	dP	dM	aP	aM	aG
	P	dM	dP	aZE	aP	aM
	ZE	dG	dM	dP	aZE	aM
	N	dE	dG	dM	dP	aZE
	NG	dE	dE	dG	dP	dP

Table 4- Rule table for $e_x = ZE$.

Δa_{ref}		e_a				
		NG	N	ZE	P	PG
e_v	PG	aZE	aP	aM	aG	aG
	P	dM	aZE	aP	aM	aM
	ZE	dM	dP	aZE	aP	aM
	N	dM	dM	dP	aM	aM
	NG	dG	dG	dM	aG	aG

Figure 16- Control surface for fuzzy output.

Using the linguistic fuzzy terms, the highlighted rules in Tables 1 and 2, can be read, respectively, as follows, by (10) and (11).

$$\text{If } e_x = P \text{ and } e_v = N \text{ and } \forall e_a \quad (10) \\ \text{then } \Delta v_{ref} = vZE$$

$$\text{If } e_x = P \text{ and } e_v = ZE \text{ and } e_a = P \quad (11) \\ \text{then } \Delta a_{ref} = aM$$

The Figures 15 and 16 show the corresponding control surfaces obtained by simulation of the developed fuzzy controller, using the Fuzzy Logic Toolbox[®] in Matlab/Simulink[®] environment by MathWorks.

Figure 15- Control surface for fuzzy output Δv_{ref} .

4. Hardware implementation

The fuzzy controller and the electromechanical position drive implementations are shown in Figure 19. The single DOF electromechanical position drive is constituted by a PM-TLSM as the linear electromechanical actuator, position drive controller with vectorial control and the digital linear encoder as the feedback device with resolution of 1 pulse/ μm . The speed feedback value is computed through the microprocessor of the position drive controller. The PM-TLSM is in a vertical position withstanding a load stack.

The fuzzy controller is programmed in a graphical language using software LabVIEW[®] developed by National Instruments.

The communication unit is a real-time industrial controller with 266MHz processing frequency developed by National Instruments. This communication unit is used to generate the trajectory reference and receives the actual position and speed values, through DeviceNet communication. Then it calculates the position, speed and acceleration errors and sends these errors to fuzzy controller, implemented into the desktop computer, through TCP-IP communication.

Figure 19- Fuzzy controller and the electromechanical position drive implementation.

The acceleration feedback is computed from speed signal using a discrete approximation of the derivative and using a moving average noise filter, which leads to a small delay in system response.

5. Experimental results

Figures 20 to 23 show the experimental results for various loads, obtained from single DOF (heave movement) electromechanical position drive with fuzzy controller.

The experimental test has been carried out to sinusoidal and triangular trajectories.

The Figures 20 to 23 represent the position reference, x_{ref} , the actual position, x , and the position error, e_x . The vertical gain is $\frac{200}{6} \times 10^{-3}$ m/div. The instant time that fuzzy controller starts the control action is marked by the vertical dashed line.

The experimental results demonstrate that the trajectory correction is made with a delay less than 1s.

The Figures 20 and 21 show the experimental results for frequency of 0,5Hz with a 130N and 740N load force respectively.

Figure 20- Position response with a 130N load force with frequency of 0,5Hz.

Figure 21- Position response with a 740N load force with frequency of 0,5Hz.

The Figures 22 and 23 show the experimental results for frequency of 1Hz with a 130N and 740N load forces respectively.

Figure 22- Position response with a 130N load force with frequency of 1Hz.

Figure 23- Position response with a 740N load force with frequency of 1Hz.

Analysing the maximum relative position errors for the experimental tests with sinusoidal trajectory, it is verified that these are between 40% and 60% before the fuzzy controller starts. After the trajectory correction period, the maximum relative position errors decrease to 9%. The experimental tests with triangular trajectory, after the trajectory correction transient period, shows that the position errors have a relative error of 10%, when the change of speed signal occurs, and have a relative error of 5%, in the constant speed periods.

These results give a comparison between the presented method and the standard PID algorithm of the position drive controller, which operates during the time before the fuzzy controller starts. Comparing the experimental results with different loads, it is verified that the position errors values does not depend of the load force applied to the tubular linear motor shaft.

6. Conclusions

The development of this fuzzy controller had the purpose to obtain the automatic adjustment of the electromechanical position drive trajectory, based on the alteration of its speed and acceleration references. The importance of this work is related with the applicability of this type of linear motors in parallel manipulators. The difficulties of these applications are the absence of trajectory planning,

which is common in parallel manipulator applications.

The experimental results show that the motor with the fuzzy control is robust, because the position errors don't increase, when different load forces are applied at different frequencies. All the experimental results display a position response delay less than 100ms caused by acceleration loop control.

The structure of the laboratory prototype of the fuzzy controller coupled to the electromechanical linear position drive was presented. The experimental results obtained are useful to evaluate the performance of the fuzzy controller, and to demonstrate the applicability of the proposed fuzzy controller.

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